

Kerala Cultural Symbolism-Impact and Influence on Purchase Intention

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Abstract : Kerala, known as “God’s Own Country,” boasts a unique cultural heritage deeply rooted in traditions, art forms, and iconic elements. This study investigates how cultural symbolism in Kerala affects consumers’ intent to buy. The study shows that cultural symbolism is crucial in influencing consumers’ views and purchase decisions by using a qualitative research approach. The findings offer insightful information for marketers, decision-makers, and advocates of cultural preservation by deepening our understanding of the connection between cultural symbolism and consumer behaviour. Consumer purchase intentions and various elements responsible for cultural symbolism were analysed in detail. Non parametric statistical tools such as Mann Whitney U test, Kruskal Wallis H test and Fried man test were employed for the analysis of the data.

Keywords : Cultural Symbolism, Purchase Intention.

Introduction

Kerala, also known as “God’s Own Country,” is a land of incredible diversity and a deep cultural history. Despite only making up a small portion of South India, Kerala is renowned for its rich past, which is a result of considerable interaction between many groups. The culture of Kerala is distinct and rich in cultural artefacts. Classical performing arts that date back to centuries, vibrant folk-art forms, folklores and rituals, martial arts, Festivals, Ayurveda, Agriculture, Language and Literature, Gold, the Spices, Cuisine, Clothing style, Crafts, Coconut products, Aranmula metal mirror etc are a few among the quintessential symbols of Kerala culture. Kerala is one of the world’s top tourist destinations

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because of its distinctive culture and customs, as well as its distinctive demographics.

Traditions can have a significant and long-lasting influence on how people think. Marketers are becoming more conscious of the need to enhance communications with groups from various cultural backgrounds in this period of fierce competition. Advertising has a close relationship to the prevailing cultural context in society and is frequently claimed that advertising from that era represent contemporary culture of society. The viewers may be drawn to the content of commercials for a variety of reasons, such as the values that the ads promote, the inventiveness with which the content is presented, the humour present, the similarity to the viewer's real life, or other considerations. Due of the emotional attachment that Keralites have to their cultural past, the portrayal of these symbols in product advertisements is seen to have a big impact on consumer purchase intentions. Therefore, it will be useful to know whether such symbols will be able to significantly catch consumer attention from the advertiser's perspective.

As customers are exposed to an overwhelming volume of commercials everywhere they turn, the idea of incorporating symbolic effects into advertisements is becoming more important and may increase consumer memory. Each brand has a distinctive symbol and when used properly, it can convey the intended values to the target market. Whether the cultural symbols employed in advertisements have the desired effect on influencing customers' purchase intentions is to be examined as advertising is a cultural product in that it both impacts and is impacted by society.

Kerala's marketing environment undergoes unmatched developments. The brand strategies used today should adjust to the Kerala framework adding functional value to a brand due to how distinctive and reflective these changes are. Any brand's strategy that connects consumers with the brand's offer must take into account cultural factors. In recent years, a few prominent companies have found success by fusing cultural significance with functional utility highlighting how these cultural prides are symbolized, how they are used in product ads, and how effective they are at swaying consumer choice.

Theoretical Review

The review of literature supported in the proper evaluation of various aspects of the topic and was useful in gaining more clarity and consciousness on the

cultural symbolism in commercials. Various research works and scholarly journal articles were studied, and the topic's context was developed. *Sharma Sangeetha (2020)* aimed to create a paradigm for depicting culture in commercials by taking into account rituals, attire, language, jingoism, festivity, religion, and so on and a model was constructed, and the impact on recall was established. *Michaelidou, N., Micevski, M., & Halkias, G (2020)* investigated how advertisers employ consumer culture positioning tactics in advertising across nations and product categories. To explore the use of such tactics and symbols, a content analysis approach was used. According to the findings of this study, global consumer culture positioning and local consumer culture positioning commercials rely more on implicit symbols. *Chiorean DM (2018)* interpreted the dynamics of symbols and their functions in advertising and explains that symbols offer a range of values to the viewers and in case of brands, symbols convert the target messages to a standing code. *Srivastava, E., Maheswarappa, S.S. and Sivakumaran, B. (2017)* examined how the nostalgia presented in TV advertisements influences information disclosure, level of involvement, type of products and stages in product life cycle. 700 advertisements from top five TV channels were selected based on the gross viewership and its content were analysed. The study found out that nostalgic ads use low information disclosure and are more commonly used for low involvement products, experience products and non-durables. Also, nostalgic appeals are more commonly used at maturity stage of PLC. *Eiman Negm, Passent Tantawi (2015)* investigated the impact of visual designs on consumer's perception and analysis suggested that pictorial elements in advertisements evoke a diverse set of meanings and it helps in developing viewers perspectives on the brands. *Petrovici Iasmina (2014)* revealed that Ad images represents a social context strongly confused with cultural values. Furthermore, author opined that symbol are effective means of conveying advertisement message and ultimately it will capture target audience attention.

Research Gap and Rationale of the Study

Consumer views, attitudes, and behaviours are heavily influenced by cultural symbolism. It is an effective instrument for people to express their cultural identities and affiliations. Consumers frequently identify cultural symbols with distinct meanings, feelings, and experiences, which can influence their assessment and choice for products or services. Previous research has shown the impact of cultural symbolism on several elements of consumer behaviour, including brand selection, product evaluation, and purchase intent. Furthermore, a significant body of literature was found elucidating the relationship between

cultural values and message strategies, culture specific market communications etc. Through the review of literatures, it was identified that the key question of impact of Kerala Cultural Symbols and Purchase intentions remain unexplored. The propensity or willingness of consumers to purchase a specific product or service is referred to as purchase intention. By invoking emotions, providing a sense of authenticity, and harmonising with consumers' cultural identities, cultural symbolism can dramatically affect purchase intention. Consumers generally regard products or brands related with cultural symbols as more significant, real, and desired, according to research. Cultural symbols can operate as cues, eliciting pleasant associations and increasing purchase desire. Furthermore, cultural symbolism can increase the perceived worth of a product or service, making it more appealing and engaging to consumers Hence the study is titled as *Kerala cultural Symbolism, its impact and influence on purchase intention*.

Statement of the Problem

Academic research has largely acknowledged the impact of cultural symbolism on consumer behaviour. Cultural symbolism refers to the meanings, values, and connotations attached to cultural components such as traditions, rituals, art forms, and symbols. The study is titled as *Kerala cultural Symbolism, its impact and influence on purchase intention*. The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between Kerala's rich cultural symbolism and its impact and influence on customer purchasing intent. The study revolves around how cultural symbolism influences consumer behaviour and influences buying decisions by evaluating relevant studies. Signs and symbols represent the meaning of communication, and culture is a vital aspect of consumer perception. As a result, the study attempts to solve is whether Kerala culture-related symbols utilised in product marketing are helpful in influencing consumer purchasing decisions. Addressing this problem will give much insight to the level of influence to traditionality in the modern advertisements and the effectiveness of cultural symbols in successfully capturing the consumer's mind.

Objectives of the Study

- To analyse the impact of Kerala Cultural Symbolism in product advertisements.
- To identify the elements connected with Kerala Traditional Culture in product advertisements.

- To evaluate the influence of Kerala Cultural Symbols in the Purchase Intention of consumers.

Scope & Significance of the Study

Most marketing activities are essentially concerned rendering of ordinary into something special. Accordingly, successful advertisements are about creating an emotional connection between the products and the customers. The present study examines the impact of Kerala cultural symbolism in the advertisements and whether it conveys the product message to the target market along with creating a sense of trust and confidence regarding content transferred. The study also throw light on the aspect whether there is any emotional influence attached with Kerala Cultural symbolism and also will give details on the level of appeal such symbols are able to evoke in relation to the Ad effectiveness.

Hypotheses

H₀ : There is no significant difference in the opinion of consumers on the impact of Kerala Cultural Symbolism in Purchase intentions based on Product Knowledge, Product Preference, Emotional Connectivity and Brand Attractiveness on the basis of a) Gender b) Age.

H₀ : There is no significant difference in the Purchase Intention of consumers and Kerala cultural symbolism in Product Advertisements on the basis of a) Gender b) Age.

H₀ : There is no significant difference among consumers in identifying the elements connected with Kerala Cultural Symbolism in Product Advertisements.

Research Methodology

The research presented here is a descriptive and analytical study to examine the impact of Kerala Cultural Symbolism impact and influence on purchase intentions using a sample survey method. Analyses of impact on purchase intention was based on four variables such as product knowledge, product preference, emotional connectivity and brand attractiveness. Efforts were also put into to analyse the elements connected with Kerala cultural symbolism. Twelve factors such as Traditional Performing Arts, Rituals, Values and Beliefs, Agriculture, Ayurveda, Monuments, Festivals, Handicrafts, Ethnic Cuisine, Spices, Dressing and Language were analysed for understanding the most influencing factor for the purchase. The data was gathered using both primary

and secondary sources. Structured questionnaires were used to collect primary data. Secondary data sources included books, research papers, journal articles, previous theses, websites, and so on. The population for the study was consumers in the Kottayam district. The study's samples were drawn through google form from the Kottayam district's population using the non-probability convenience sampling method. The sample size was set at 280. Statistical software such as SPSS 20 and Microsoft Excel served for analysis. Non parametric tests such as Mann Whitney U Test, Kruskal Wallis H Test and Friedman test were applied.

Limitations of the Study

The study faced constraints as it was confined to selected sample respondents from the Kottayam district. The inherent limitations of statistical tools also affected degree of accuracy of results. Only the consumers were approached for the study. The advertising agencies and the Companies were not included.

Analysis and Discussion of the Results

The objectives were analysed using hypotheses on impact of Kerala cultural symbolism in Purchase intentions based on four variables such as product knowledge, product preference, emotional connectivity and brand attractiveness. Efforts were also put into to analyse the elements connected with Kerala cultural symbolism. Mann Whitney U test Kruskal Wallis H test and Fried man test were used for proper analysis and arriving at conclusions.

H0 : There is no significant difference in the opinion of consumers on the impact of Kerala Cultural Symbolism in Purchase intentions based on Product Knowledge, Product Preference, Emotional Connectivity and Brand Attractiveness on the basis of a) Gender b) Age

Table-1 highlights the impact of Kerala Cultural Symbolism on the basis of gender. As per the mean score of the responses about Product Knowledge, Product Preference, Emotional Connectivity and Brand Attractiveness, the mean score variation between male and female is not statistically significant at 5 percent level of significance ($p > 0.05$). Hence the researcher fails to reject the null hypothesis.

Table-2 detail out the impact of Kerala Cultural Symbolism on the basis of age. As per the mean score of the responses about, Product preference, Emotional connectivity and Brand attractiveness the mean score variation between ages is not statistically significant at 5 percent level of significance ($p > 0.05$). But it is

found statistically significant for Product Knowledge where the mean score shows that age group of 40- 60 years have better product knowledge than other groups. ($p < 0.05$, 77.50). Hence it can be concluded that impact is equal with respect to gender and age.

H0 : There is no significant difference in the Purchase Intention of consumers and Kerala cultural symbolism in Product Advertisements on the basis of a) Gender b) Age

Table-3 shows the Purchase Intention of consumers and Kerala cultural symbolism in Product Advertisements on the basis of gender. As per the mean score of the responses about purchase intention, the mean score variation between male and female is not statistically significant at 5 percent level of significance ($p > 0.05$). Hence the researcher fails to reject the null hypothesis

Table-4 shows the Purchase Intention of consumers and Kerala cultural symbolism in Product Advertisements on the basis of age. As per the mean score of the responses about purchase intention, the mean score variation between ages is not statistically significant at 5 percent level of significance ($p > 0.05$). Hence the researcher fails to reject the null hypothesis. Hence it can be concluded that purchase intention is equal with respect to gender and age.

H0 : There is no significant difference among consumers in identifying the elements connected with Kerala Cultural Symbolism in Product Advertisements.

It is evident from Table 5 that the element Traditional Performing Arts shows the lowest mean (3.2167) followed by Rituals (4.6333). Variable having lowest mean should be ranked first. Hence it may be concluded that, in the opinion of consumers, Traditional Performing Arts and secondly Rituals are best in representing Kerala Culture in product advertisements. This mean rank variation is significant at 5 percent level of significance. (Value of Chi-Square is 366.436 with $p < 0.000 < 0.05$). Hence the researcher rejects the null hypothesis.

Conclusion:

The current study on Kerala Cultural Symbolism in Product Advertisements demonstrates that cultural symbols have a major influence on customer mindset. An examination of the impact of Kerala cultural Symbolism on the basis of demographic characteristics was performed, and the results revealed that there is no significant difference in gender and age of respondents. Impact was

evaluated using four variables such as product knowledge, product choice, emotional connectivity, and brand attractiveness but the variable product knowledge showed a significant difference in the age wise analysis and it was spotted among the age group of 40-60years. Numerous aspects associated with cultural symbolism in advertising were identified, and the feelings associated with these symbols were assessed. Traditional performing arts were discovered to be the most popular Kerala cultural symbol and a sense of belonging. There are more areas to be explored in the topic as one can study each element with purchase intention.

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Appendices:

Table-1 : Test Statistics on the Impact of Kerala Cultural Symbolism on the basis of Gender

Variables	Gender of the Respondents	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mann Whitney U	z	Sig.
Product Knowledge	Male	60.05	2462.00	1601.000	-0.103	0.918
	Female	60.73	4798.00			
Product Preference	Male	57.90	2374.00	1513.000	-0.593	0.553
	Female	61.85	4886.00			
Emotional Connectivity	Male	59.18	2426.50	1565.500	-0.300	0.764
	Female	61.18	4833.50			
Brand Attractiveness	Male	59.98	2459.00	1598.000	-0.120	0.905
	Female	60.77	4801.00			

a. Mann Whitney U Test b. Grouping Variable: Gender of Respondents

Table-2 : Test Statistics on the Impact of Kerala Cultural Symbolism on the basis of Age

Variables	Age of Respondents	Mean Rank	Chi-square	df	Sig.
Product Knowledge	Below 20 years	50.67	8.658	3	0.034*
	20-40 years	56.46			
	40-60 years	77.50*			
	Above 60 years	66.92			
Product Preference	Below 20 years	54.97	2.271	3	0.518
	20-40 years	58.51			
	40-60 years	68.02			
	Above 60 years	69.33			
Emotional Connectivity	Below 20 years	50.11	3.771	3	0.287
	20-40 years	60.35			
	40-60 years	70.08			
	Above 60 years	53.58			
Brand Attractiveness	Below 20 years	55.58	2.204	3	0.531
	20-40 years	58.82			
	40-60 years	69.38			
	Above 60 years	58.17			

a. Kruskal Wallis H Test b. Grouping Variable: Age of Respondents

Table-3 : Test Statistics on the Purchase Intention of consumers and Kerala cultural symbolism in Product Advertisements on the basis of Gender

Variable	Gender	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mann Whitney U	Z	df	Sig.
Purchase Intention	Male	62.02	2543.00	1557.000	-0.348	1	0.728
	Female	59.71	4717.00				

a. Mann Whitney U Test b. Grouping Variable: Gender of Respondents

Table-4 : Test Statistics on the Purchase Intention of consumers and Kerala cultural symbolism in Product Advertisements on the basis of Age

Variable	Age of Respondents	Mean Rank	Chi-square	df	Sig.
Purchase Intention	Below 20 years	57.22	0.409	3	0.938
	20-40 years	61.63			
	40-60 years	61.04			
	Above 60 years	54.75			

a. Kruskal Wallis H Test b. Grouping Variable: Age of Respondents

Table-5 : Statement showing Mean Rank and Table showing Test Statistics

Elements	Mean Rank	N	Chi-Square	df	Asymp. Sig.
Traditional Performing Arts	3.2167	280	366.436	11	0.000*
Rituals	4.6333				
Values and Beliefs	4.7917				
Agriculture	5.0083				
Ayurveda	5.3000				
Monuments	7.2083				
Festivals	6.1750				
Handicrafts	7.2750				
Ethnic Cuisine	8.4750				
Spices	8.5417				
Dressing	8.6583				
Language	8.7167				

Friedman Test